

Optimizing indoor air quality in hospitals with special reference to carbon dioxide

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Abstract

Maintaining optimal CO₂ levels in patient wards is crucial for ensuring the health and safety of patients and healthcare staffs. This paper explores the various factors that influence CO₂ levels in critical patient wards such as ICUs, burn wards, and operating theatres of Behala Balananda Brahmachari Hospital and Research Centre in Kolkata (India). Factors such as ventilation, patient density, the presence of indoor plants, room occupancy, and design are discussed. Additionally, permissible CO₂ levels are examined based on guidelines from the World Health Organization (WHO), Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), and the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE). Effective strategies for monitoring and managing CO₂ levels are also outlined. The present paper has great significance as CO₂ level within the healthcare units impacts the health and wellbeing of the patients.

Keywords: Behala Balananda Brahmachari Hospital and Research Centre in Kolkata (India), CO₂ levels, Patient wards, Safety and Health of patients.

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1. Introduction

The CO₂ levels in patient wards play a significant role in maintaining indoor air quality, which is vital for patient recovery and staff performance. Elevated CO₂ levels can lead to adverse health effects, including headaches, dizziness, and impaired cognitive function. Understanding the factors that influence CO₂ levels and adhering to recommended standards is essential for creating a safe healthcare environment. The main factors that regulate the CO₂ level within the indoor environment of the hospital are pointed here in brief.

1.1 Ventilation

Ventilation systems are critical in controlling CO₂ levels in patient wards. Proper ventilation ensures a constant supply of fresh air and the removal of exhaled CO₂. There are two main types of ventilation: natural and mechanical. Natural ventilation involves the use of windows, doors, and other openings that allow air to flow naturally through the ward. The effectiveness of natural ventilation depends on the building design, outdoor air quality, and weather conditions. Mechanical ventilation includes HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) systems, which are designed to maintain specific indoor air quality standards. These systems can be calibrated to ensure optimal CO₂ levels by adjusting airflow rates and filtration systems [1].

1.2 Number of Patients

The number of patients in a ward directly impacts CO₂ levels. Each patient exhales CO₂, contributing to the overall concentration. More patients lead to higher CO₂ levels. Additionally, patients with higher metabolic rates, such as those with fever, may produce more CO₂ [2].

1.3 Presence of Indoor Plants

Indoor plants can influence CO₂ levels through photosynthesis, where they absorb CO₂ and release oxygen. The effectiveness of plants in reducing CO₂ levels depends on the type and number of plants as shown in Figure 1. High-density planting can significantly impact air quality [3].

Indoor plants that are known for producing more oxygen and improving air quality include:

- I. **Areca Palm (*Dyopsis lutescens*)**: Excellent at producing oxygen and removing toxins

from the air. It also acts as a natural humidifier.

- II. **Spider Plant (*Chlorophytum comosum*)**: Efficient at absorbing carbon monoxide and formaldehyde, while releasing a significant amount of oxygen.

- III. **Aloe Vera (*Aloe barbadensis miller*)**: Produces oxygen and purifies the air by removing benzene and formaldehyde.

- IV. **Boston Fern (*Nephrolepis exaltata*)**: Known for producing oxygen and acting as a natural air purifier by removing pollutants like formaldehyde and xylene.

- V. **Peace Lily (*Spathiphyllum*)**: Produces oxygen and filters out harmful toxins like ammonia, benzene, and formaldehyde.

- VI. **Pothos (*Epipremnum aureum*)**: Also known as devil's ivy, Pothos releases oxygen while removing indoor air toxins like formaldehyde, benzene, and xylene.

- VII. **Chinese evergreen (*Aglaonema*)**: Highly effective at removing toxins and is a good oxygen producer.

- VIII. **Weeping Figure (*Ficus benjamina*)**: Increases oxygen levels and removes common indoor air pollutants like formaldehyde and benzene.

- IX. **Money Plant (*Epipremnum aureum*)**: Commonly known as money plant, it is easy to care for, produces oxygen, and filters out indoor air toxins like formaldehyde and benzene.

- X. **Snake Plant (*Sansevieria trifasciata*)**: Also known as mother-in-law's tongue, it is one of the best plants for increasing oxygen levels, especially at night, and is also effective at removing toxins like formaldehyde and benzene.

1.4 Room Occupancy and Activity Levels

The presence and activity level of healthcare staffs also contribute to CO₂ levels. High activity levels can increase respiration rates and thus CO₂ production. During visiting hours, the additional presence of visitors can temporarily elevate CO₂ levels [4].

1.5 Room Size and Design

The volume of space and room design, including the placement of windows, doors, and ventilation systems, affect air circulation and CO₂ distribution. Larger rooms with higher ceilings can dilute CO₂ more effectively than smaller, enclosed spaces [1].

Maintaining CO₂ levels within permissible limits is crucial for patient safety and comfort. Various health organizations provide guidelines on acceptable CO₂ levels in indoor environments.

The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that indoor CO₂ concentrations should not exceed 1000 ppm to ensure adequate indoor air quality and prevent adverse health effects [5].

Figure 1: Indoor plants in health care units.

Source: Authors.

Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) sets permissible exposure limits (PELs) for workplace environments. For CO₂, OSHA's PEL is 5000 ppm over an 8-hour workday. However, for healthcare settings, lower levels are advised to accommodate sensitive populations such as patients.

American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) recommends maintaining indoor CO₂ levels below 1000 ppm for optimal indoor air quality in

healthcare facilities. ASHRAE Standard 62.1 outlines ventilation requirements to achieve these levels [1].

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, conducted during 20th July, 2024 to 22nd July, 2024 CO₂ levels indoors have been monitored using a small indoor CO₂ analyser (Figure 2). The analyser has been positioned at breathing height, approximately 3-5 feet from the floor, in the selected monitoring area, ensuring placement away from windows, doors, and direct airflow sources to avoid skewed readings. Calibration has been performed according to the manufacturer's instructions, typically requiring a zero or span gas calibration. The device has been powered on and allowed to warm up for a few minutes as recommended.

Figure 2: CO₂ analyzer for monitoring CO₂ in the indoor environment

Source: Authors.

Continuous monitoring of CO₂ levels has been conducted over at least 4 hours in the day time for 2 days. The data logging feature has been utilized to record CO₂ levels at regular intervals, typically every minute. The recorded data have been analyzed to identify patterns and peak CO₂ levels.

Readings have been compared with standards such as ASHRAE’s recommendation of keeping indoor CO₂ levels below 1000 ppm. A report summarizing the findings, including average, peak, and minimum CO₂ levels over the monitoring period, has been generated.

Regular recalibrations of the analyser and sensor replacement have been conducted to ensure ongoing accuracy. Based on the findings, necessary recommendations to improve ventilation and reduce CO₂ concentrations have been suggested where high levels have been detected. This methodical approach has ensured effective monitoring and standardization of CO₂ levels in indoor environments, contributing to a healthy and safe atmosphere at Behala Balananda Brahmachari Hospital and Research Centre.

3. Results

The ward-wise levels of CO₂, VOC, and HCHO are highlighted in Table (1). It is observed that the CO₂ level in the indoor wards varied as per the order general female ward (1385 ppm) > dialysis ward (1094 ppm) > ICCU & CCU (1055 ppm) > male general ward (847 ppm) > labour ward (483 ppm) > personal cabin (460 ppm) > private female ward (413 ppm) > private cabin female (410 ppm) > private ward male (409 ppm) > NICU and pediatrics (408 ppm).

The VOC level in the indoor wards varied as per the order dialysis ward (1.045 mg/m³) > emergency ward (0.740 mg/m³) > NICU and pediatrics (0.423 mg/m³) > ICCU & CCU (0.403 mg/m³) > male general ward (0.233 mg/m³) > labour ward (0.039 mg/m³) > personal cabin (0.027 mg/m³) > private female ward and general female ward (0.024 mg/m³) > personal cabin female (0.021 mg/m³) > private ward male (0.017 mg/m³).

Table 1: Ward-wise levels of CO₂, VOC, and HCHO.

S.No.	Wards	Coordinates	CO ₂ (ppm)	VOC (mg/m ³)	HCHO (mg/m ³)
1.	Private Ward Male Dormitory (1 patient)	22°30'23.3"N 88°19'13.6"E	409	0.017	0.013
2.	Private Ward Female Dormitory (3 patients)	22°30'23.4"N 88°19'14.2"E	413	0.024	0.007
3.	Private Cabin Female (2 patients)	22°30'23.6"N 88°19'14.7"E	410	0.021	0.013
4.	ICCU & CCU (13 patients)	22°30'24.0"N 88°19'14.7"E	1055	0.403	0.070
5.	Male General Ward (12 patients)	22°30'24.0"N 88°19'14.7"E	847	0.233	0.041
6.	Labour Ward (1 patient)	22°30'24.2"N 88°19'14.7"E	483	0.039	0.009
7.	Dialysis Ward (12 patients)	22°30'24.0"N 88°19'14.7"E	1094	1.045	0.182
8.	General Female Ward (19 patients)	22°30'24.0"N 88°19'14.7"E	1385	0.024	0.006
9.	Operation Theatre (OT) (0 patient)	22°30'23.3"N 88°19'13.6"E	NM	NM	NM
10.	NICU (0 patient)	22°30'24.2"N 88°19'14.7"E	408	0.423	0.076
11.	Pediatrics Ward (1 patient)	22°30'24.2"N 88°19'14.7"E	408	0.423	0.076
12.	Personal Cabin No. 8 (1 patient)	22°30'24.2"N 88°19'14.7"E	460	0.027	0.009
13.	Emergency Ward (0 patient) CONTROL	22°30'24.0"N 88°19'14.6"E	NM	0.740	0.133

Note: Volatile Organic Carbon (VOC) mg/m³; NM means ‘Not measured’ as there were no patients. **Source:** Authors.

The HCHO level in the indoor wards varied as per the order dialysis ward (0.182 mg/m³) > emergency ward (0.133 mg/m³) > NICU and pediatrics (0.076 mg/m³) > ICCU & CCU (0.070 mg/m³) > male general ward (0.041 mg/m³) > private ward male and private cabin female (0.013 mg/m³) > labour ward and personal cabin (0.009 mg/m³) > private female ward (0.007 mg/m³) > general female ward (0.006 mg/m³).

In addition to this the table also highlights the total number of patients recorded to evaluate the inter-relationship between the number of patients and the environmental parameters. The correlation coefficient between the total number of patients and the parameters are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation Coefficient between the indoor environment variables and number of patients.

	CO ₂	VOC	HCHO	Patients
CO ₂	1			
VOC	0.027835	1		
HCHO	0.001916	0.998667	1	
Patients	0.937159	0.127751	0.09949	1
Significant at 1% level i.e. p < 0.01				

Source: Authors.

4. Discussions

Indoor air quality in healthcare settings is critical for patient health and recovery. Hospitals, with their enclosed environments and diverse populations, are particularly sensitive to air quality issues. One of the significant components affecting indoor air quality is CO₂, a colorless, odorless gas naturally present in the atmosphere. While CO₂ at low concentrations is harmless, elevated levels can pose health risks, particularly in confined spaces like hospital wards. This paper aims to evaluate the effects of CO₂ concentration in hospital interiors on patient well-being, exploring the mechanisms by which CO₂ levels can impact health and suggesting potential mitigation strategies.

Indoor air quality in hospitals is influenced by several factors, including ventilation, occupancy levels, and activities performed within the space. According to the World Health Organization

(WHO), maintaining optimal indoor air quality is essential to prevent the spread of airborne diseases and to ensure the comfort and well-being of patients and staff [5]. Poor indoor air quality can exacerbate respiratory conditions, contribute to the development of new health issues, and negatively affect the overall patient recovery process. CO₂ is often used as an indicator of indoor air quality. It is a byproduct of human respiration, and its levels can quickly rise in poorly ventilated spaces. The American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) recommends that indoor CO₂ levels should not exceed 1000 parts per million (ppm) to maintain good air quality [1]. However, studies have shown that CO₂ concentrations in some hospital environments can surpass these levels, especially in areas with high patient turnover and inadequate ventilation systems [4]. Elevated CO₂ levels can lead to various health issues. Short-term exposure to high concentrations of CO₂ can cause symptoms such as headaches, dizziness, and shortness of breath [2]. Long-term exposure can result in more severe health effects, including respiratory problems and cognitive impairments. In hospital settings, where patients may already be vulnerable due to their medical conditions, these health risks are particularly concerning.

A study [3] demonstrated that higher indoor CO₂ levels are associated with decreased cognitive function. This finding is significant for hospital environments, where both patients and healthcare workers need to maintain high levels of cognitive performance. For patients, impaired cognitive function can hinder recovery, while for healthcare workers, it can affect their ability to make critical decisions and provide effective care.

Ventilation is a key factor in controlling indoor CO₂ levels. Proper ventilation ensures the continuous exchange of indoor air with fresh outdoor air, diluting the concentration of CO₂ and other pollutants. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) emphasizes the importance of adequate ventilation in healthcare settings to reduce the transmission of infectious diseases and improve indoor air quality [6].

However, achieving optimal ventilation in hospitals can be challenging due to the complexity of the building designs and the need to balance air quality with energy efficiency. Studies have

shown that many hospitals struggle to maintain adequate ventilation rates, leading to elevated CO₂ levels and poor air quality [7]. Enhancing ventilation systems and adopting advanced air purification technologies can help address these issues and improve patient outcomes.

Several strategies can be employed to reduce CO₂ levels in hospital interiors and improve indoor air quality. These include:

- **Improving Ventilation Systems:** Upgrading existing ventilation systems to ensure they meet the recommended standards for air exchange rates can significantly reduce indoor CO₂ levels. This may involve installing more efficient HVAC systems, using air purifiers, and ensuring regular maintenance of ventilation equipment.
- **Increasing Natural Ventilation:** Where possible, incorporating natural ventilation using windows and vents can help reduce CO₂ concentrations. This is particularly effective in hospital areas that are not directly involved in critical patient care.
- **Monitoring and Control Systems:** Implementing real-time monitoring systems to continuously measure indoor CO₂ levels can help identify areas with poor air quality and take immediate corrective actions. Automated control systems can adjust ventilation rates based on CO₂ concentrations, ensuring optimal air quality at all times.
- **Reducing Occupancy Density:** Limiting the number of people in confined spaces can help reduce the buildup of CO₂. This may involve reorganizing patient rooms, waiting areas, and staff offices to allow for better air circulation and lower occupancy densities.
- **Green Building Design:** Incorporating green building principles in hospital design can enhance indoor air quality. This includes using materials that do not emit harmful pollutants, designing for natural light and ventilation, and creating green spaces that promote overall well-being.
- **Enhancing Indoor Air Quality through Indoor Plants:** Indoor plants play a crucial role in keeping a room fresh and oxygenated for several reasons:

I. **Oxygen Production:** Plants undergo photosynthesis, a process where they absorb

carbon dioxide (CO₂) and release oxygen (O₂) as a by-product. During the day, this increases the oxygen levels in the room, contributing to fresher air.

II. **Air Purification:** Many indoor plants can filter out toxins and pollutants from the air. For example, plants like spider plants, snake plants, and peace lilies are known to absorb chemicals like formaldehyde, benzene, and ammonia, which are commonly found in household items. This purification process results in cleaner, fresher air.

III. **Humidity Regulation:** Plants release moisture into the air through a process called transpiration. This can help to maintain indoor humidity levels, especially in dry environments, making the air feel fresher and more comfortable to breathe.

IV. **Psychological Benefits:** The presence of greenery has been shown to improve mood, reduce stress, and enhance overall well-being. A fresh, well-oxygenated environment contributes to a sense of calm and relaxation, which indirectly keeps the room feeling fresh.

V. **Reduction of Carbon Dioxide:** Plants are known to reduce the level of CO₂ in the ambient air for carrying out the process of photosynthesis leading to carbon sequestration [8 - 17]. At night, some plants can continue to absorb CO₂, even though photosynthesis is limited. This ongoing process helps in maintaining a balance of gases in the room, contributing to an overall fresher atmosphere.

VI. **Aesthetic Appeal:** Besides their health benefits, plants add a natural, soothing aesthetic to a room. This visual freshness can make a space feel more inviting and vibrant.

The corridor of the health care units may be covered with hanging herbs and shrubs as shown in Figure (2).

5. Conclusions

The document discusses the importance of maintaining optimal indoor air quality in healthcare settings, focusing on the levels of carbon CO₂ and its impact on patient well-being. Elevated CO₂ levels in hospital wards, due to poor ventilation, can lead to health risks such as respiratory issues and cognitive impairments. The

paper highlights the correlation between CO₂ levels and patient health, emphasizing the need for adequate ventilation, monitoring, and control systems. Strategies to improve air quality include upgrading ventilation systems, incorporating natural ventilation, reducing occupancy density, and using specific indoor plant species for air purification and oxygenation. Enhancing indoor air quality is critical for patient recovery and the overall effectiveness of healthcare environments.

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